

ANALYSES OF THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL TRANSLATION METHODS

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Annotation: The study of the history of translation in close connection with the history of society, culture, history of literature is also a requirement of the time. However, it would be wrong to study them how many scientists have worked. The main goal, as noted below, is to use past experiences to more accurately define our present and future lifestyles and not to repeat the mistakes made along the way.

Key words: translation, literature, art, culture, science of different peoples, foreign language, speech activities, important skills.

Introduction: Thanks to independence, the demand for learning and teaching foreign languages in our country is growing. For the further development and prosperity of our country, which today strives to take its rightful place among the developed countries of the world, for our people, who are building their great future together with our foreign partners, perfect knowledge of foreign languages is very important.

Translation is a very big and important role in human development, in its cultural life. Translation introduces people from one country or continent to the life, culture, customs, history, literature and science of people from another country. Through translation, we learn other cultures, and others learn the great Uzbek culture. If we want to understand each other's national and cultural features faster and better, we will have to translate the works of other nations.

The meaning of the word translation is very wide. Poems, works of art, scientific and popular science books in various fields of science, diplomatic documents, working papers, people's conversations, etc. are translated from one language to another. Of course, translation is the key to all of this.

Material and methods: Its scientific significance in both translation theory and the history of translation is of great interest in translation, which is its object. Translation is a creative activity related to language and literature, and the two languages are intertwined, in which the original the text is represented by other language tools. A number of questions arise with the process of comparing and translating languages. These questions, in turn, encourage them to analyze them, to study the specifics of each.

As mentioned above, translation is an activity that serves to bring together the literature, art, culture, science of different peoples. For a student learning a foreign

language, translation is all kinds of speech activities - listening, speaking, reading and writing. skills are equally important.

The study of the history of translation opens the way to a deeper understanding of this field, to the development of the science of translation and translation studies today, because it is impossible to create the future without knowing the history. It is time to seriously study these rare manuscripts, which embody the centuries-old life experiences, religious, moral and scientific views of our ancestors.

So what is the purpose of studying the history of translation? Along with the study of the history of translation, firstly, to show the contribution of Uzbek literature, scholars to the treasury of world literature, secondly, to show the role of Uzbek literature in world literature, thirdly, the role of translation in the development of world science and culture clearly visible.

These works explore the various schools of translation history from antiquity to the present day, their activities, prominent figures, and the role of translation history in the development of modern translation trends.

"Nevertheless, many major monuments in the history of translation, the work of talented translators have not been studied," said G. Ostonova.

Translation occupies a worthy place in all national literatures with a centuries-old literary tradition. Therefore, it is safe to say that without creating a history of translation, the laws of translation have developed in each period, the same national. it is impossible to give a full, complete account of the history of that national literature without defining what schools of translation were formed in the development of literature and what role these translations played in the development of world culture. In the second half of the XX century, there was a slow process of translation from Germany into France. Even English realism could not influence him, and the focus on translation was still not growing.

It is known from the history of science and culture that the exchange of ideas through translation goes back a long way. In the developed countries of the world there are large schools of translation, translation schools. In particular, R. Toldeysky's Western European school of Translation (XII century), Among them are the Russian Translation Society (XVIII century), the Baikal Wisdom (House of Knowledge) in Baghdad, the Al-Ma'mun school, the Arabic Translation school (XVII century), and the Khorezm Translation School (XIX century) (O. Muminov, translation date T.1999).

In Armenia, "Translation Day" has been celebrated every year since the 5th century. In his work, P.I. Kapanov. describes the translator as a universal and artistically harmonious representative of the peoples who serve to unite and unite people in world culture.

After that, the Uzbek writer Hamid Olimjon, Samad Qurgun, Gafur Gulam, Berdi Kerboboyev, Oybek will explain how and in what languages the works of famous writers and poets have been translated.

Result and discussion: The translation of the artistic property of the great works of the East into European languages has a long history. Interest in Eastern culture in the West dates back to the beginning of the ninth century. The southern regions of Spain, which belonged to the Arab Caliphate, had favorable conditions for the introduction of Eastern culture to the West, because at that time Europe lagged behind the East in all areas of human development. During this period, many powerful translators were able to benefit Europeans with the culture, science, art, and customs of the East by translating universal studies into Arabic into Latin.

As a result of this influence of the East on the West, new philosophical currents and freedom of speech emerged.

There were two major styles of Renaissance translation: literal translation and free translation, and there was a constant struggle between them.

At that time, Britain was also interested in oriental culture and art, and for several centuries Central Asia attracted the attention of the British. Samarkand, located on the Great Silk Road, was one of the favorite topics of English writers and poets. Famous Central Asian scholars Al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Ahmad-Al-Farghani translated great figures from Arabic into English at the time.

British tourists and traders were in contact with the countries of the East through Russia. The ancient peoples of Movaraunnahr, Samarkand and Bukhara were the centers of relations. J. Jersey, A. Jeniksok came to Bukhara and Urgench through Moscow and tried to establish trade and diplomatic relations. As a result, a number of words moved from one language to another. In the middle of the seventeenth century, Oriental centers were opened at the universities of Cambridge and Oxford in the United Kingdom, where he was taught Arabic, Turkish and Persian. This major revolutionary period in world history, especially in the history of translation and the development of languages.

After reviewing the sources on the history of translation studies, it can be said that the history of translation, especially the history of Oriental translation, has been thoroughly studied.

There is a feature associated with translation, that some scientific and artistic works are not only in the hands of one people, but also in many countries around the world, and translation plays a key role in their dissemination in the languages of other peoples. At the same time, translation sometimes serves directly and indirectly in the spread of scientific and artistic ideas, images, ideas, new views, and in the form of pictures. MM Rozhanskaya also emphasizes in her works that through translation peoples are united. - those who thought with each other, the writers who

communicated with each other. The culture, science, literature and art he has created have always benefited from the translation of literary, scientific and political works.

"But it must be reiterated that if the translation only served the purpose of making a new book appear in another language, and ending with that, it would be like the birth of a lifeless child."

Turning to the history of translation, the author writes that there were two great schools of translation in the history of world culture. One was the Baghdad School of Translation, which translated the works of ancient Greek scholars into Arabic, and the other was the translation of rich Arabic literature into Western European languages. Both schools of translation have played an unprecedented role in the development of world science. Under the influence of the East to the West, new philosophical currents emerged. Thus, the Renaissance was a period of influence in Western Europe in the history of scientific development, cultural riches, and human culture of the East.

In conclusion, it is clear from the sources on the history of translation that there is not enough research work to study the history of translation. The life experiences of our ancestors over the centuries, thousands of works on religious ethics, philosophy, medicine, mathematics, physics, chemistry, astronomy, architecture and agriculture have been translated into other languages and contributed to world science and culture. These rare works should be seriously studied and enjoyed by today's readers.

It is well known that in both the East and the West, most of the written sources are translated works. The traditions of translation and literary relations go back many centuries.

The translator has the task of translating the masterpieces of the peoples of the world into their native language and making them available to the people.

The study of translated works is also important for the study of the history of translation. Because the principles, methods and techniques of translation, which are a unique field of creativity, have been improved over time, traditions have been formed and developed, mutual benefit, influence and literary-artistic ties have increased. Therefore, it is important to study each period of the history of translation, each translation separately.

The study of the history of the world's translation schools shows that since ancient times, Eastern translators have been engaged in the translation of religious, scientific, technical, literary and artistic works published in the West and used modern principles and methods. Western scholars, in turn, introduced the teachings and scientific inventions of the great thinkers of the East to their peoples and took advantage of these achievements.

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